

As an Example for the Sustainability and Technology Use in Logistics "Lineage"

Sabire Yazıcı¹

Abstract

The close relationship of companies with sustainability and technology is of paramount importance across all sectors. To stay competitive, many companies are increasing their technological investments while simultaneously marketing their understanding of sustainability to the public. This "sustainable technology" perspective is gaining acceptance strongly in the business world. The logistics sector is one such area where these activities are observed. Logistics companies prioritize sustainability in all areas, starting with fuel consumption, while simultaneously using technology more intensively to increase the efficiency of their logistics operations. Lineage, a US-based company, is an example of a company that strives to integrate sustainability and technology in both its warehousing and logistics operations. The company not only uses these two elements in its own operations but also develops solutions for various business partners, stakeholders, and customers. This research examines the striking sustainability and technology-focused activities in the operations of Lineage, one of the rare companies that combines sustainability and technology and is among the top companies in the world in terms of revenue.

Keywords: Competition, Logistics, Sustainable Technology, Sustainability, Technology, Warehousing

Submission Date: 12.01.2026

Acceptance Date: 25.02.2026

Cite: Yazıcı, S. (2026). As an Example for the Sustainability and Technology Use in Logistics "Lineage", Edunorm Journal, 2(1), 16-26.

¹ Istanbul Beykent University, Freelance Writer, e-mail: sabireyazici@gmail.com, ORCID ID 0000-0003-3464-371X

Introduction

The logistics sector is one of the business areas with the greatest financial potential, the highest employment rate, and also the highest energy consumption worldwide. In recent years, many actors within the logistics sector, from warehousing systems to reaching the end user, have been able to access very different parts of the world. The activities of these actors create significant financial potential, but also bring with them a major problem of energy resource consumption. Particularly when considered from the perspective of cold chain storage and cold chain logistics, it is evident that companies in the sector have become significant energy consumers in both storage and transportation. Therefore, sustainability is becoming increasingly important in the logistics sector.

The increasing importance of sustainability in the logistics sector is particularly noteworthy due to the prominence of food and pharmaceutical storage and transportation activities in the post-Covid-19 period. During this period, it is possible to see that cold chain logistics have reached a critical point from a storage perspective. However, while the world's needs in terms of cold chain storage and cold chain logistics are significant, it has also been recognized that these logistics activities require innovative approaches to energy consumption and process management. Many companies that have combined technological elements with the logistics sector have made significant progress in terms of sustainability while also visibly improving their operational quality.

The US-based company Lineage stands out as a key player in this sector, making a difference nationally, regionally and globally. With the innovative technologies it has developed in recent years, the company creates innovative solutions in cold chain storage and cold chain logistics, both for itself and for its business partners in the sector. The company, which has made significant strides, particularly in software and artificial intelligence, plays a pioneering role worldwide. Lineage, which integrates sustainability in cold chain logistics with technology, building many logistics activities, especially warehousing, on a foundation of digital tools and systems, is highlighted as the focus of this study.

Cold Chain Storage and Logistics

Cold chain logistics, a key element among innovative logistics types, is not only important for manufacturers and transporters but also holds a significant place in government trade and economic policies. In addition to food products, cold chain logistics applications, which prevent high temperature pressure during the storage and transportation of various elements, especially pharmaceuticals, in the medical field, enable ventilation systems in fixed locations to be implemented during transportation (Saravanan & Anubama, 2017).

On the other hand, while cold chain logistics utilizes cooling systems similar to those used at fixed locations for elements requiring cold air support, the crucial aspect of the process is the sustainability of these cooling systems. In other words, faced with longer distances and increasing waiting times, cold chain transportation stands out as a type of logistics that adopts the use of the most efficient and durable cooling mechanism as its fundamental principle (Wang, 2016).

In terms of quality, temperature control and energy consumption are the most important factors determining the requirements of cold chain logistics. Throughout the process, starting with storage and continuing with product transportation, monitoring and managing temperature values and energy consumption amounts from a central location are critical applications. Although all companies involved in the cold chain want every stage of their logistics processes to be carried out in a healthy and cost-effective manner, there are practices that are particularly important regarding energy consumption and cannot be ignored (Pindi, 2025).

Cold chain logistics, in terms of quality, is a type of logistics that generally depends on the quality and durability of the transport vehicles within the transportation companies. In this logistics application, transport vehicles, acting as carrier cold storage facilities, possess robust mechanisms to ensure that the goods they carry remain in excellent condition and healthy for extended periods. Cold chain logistics, which is heavily integrated with technology, meticulously addresses the safety of transported goods (Yuen, 2017).

In cold chain transportation, a crucial aspect is determining the level of cooling required for the transported goods and identifying the appropriate technological elements to be used during this process. Cold chain transportation, in this context, is the logistics practice that can maintain the lowest possible temperature for the longest possible time to the transported goods. In other words, the robustness and sustainability of the cooling method in terms of process is considered a fundamental task of cold chain transportation (Fuente and Ros, 2010).

In the global market, understanding the management tools needed in supply chain logistics and improving the visibility of flows within the network is essential. For visibility, monitoring temperature changes during transport of perishable foods is crucial. In addition, temperature control is crucial for maintaining product quality and quantity at the end of the supply chain. Cold logistics management is defined as the process of planning, executing, controlling, efficiently managing the flow, and storing of perishable foods from one or more information and service centers at production, distribution, and consumption points to meet customer needs on a global scale (Bogataj, Bogataj & Vodopivec, 2005).

Storage systems are crucial for the efficient implementation of cold chain logistics. Both stationary and mobile storage facilities mounted on vehicles must possess the necessary cooling capabilities. Since the early years of cold chain logistics, the improvement in the cooling capabilities of fixed and vehicle storage facilities has provided a significant advantage, particularly in terms of remote control and intervention in these facilities, taking the system to a new level (Thompson, 2016).

Cold storage facilities and their management play a significant role in the industry as a whole. The variability of product diversity, coupled with the threat of global warming, necessitates consideration of varying temperature settings. Therefore, the use of technological elements has become a necessity to prevent the complex processes and calculations related to temperature management in cold chain storage facilities from becoming a problem. At the same time, technological support in space allocation in warehouses and the determination of appropriate temperature values points to an issue that the cold chain needs (Beldar, 2025).

Throughout the process, manufacturers and transport companies, in parallel with their investments in cooling systems, prefer to use access methods that allow them not only to intervene in a fixed manner but also to intervene remotely when necessary (Azira, Norhayati and Norwati, 2013).

On the other hand, digital systems that enable remote access to vehicles are supportive in protecting products and their inherent qualities. Remote access systems, in particular, enable manufacturers and logistics companies to improve their ability to manage processes efficiently and successfully in cold chain logistics (Thompson, 2016).

Sustainability and Technology in the Cold Chain

Many activities involved in cold chain storage and cold chain logistics necessitate the use of technology. While technology is an indispensable element for the cold chain, it negatively alters the process conditions and creates adverse environmental impacts due to increased energy consumption. The cost of innovative and sustainable technologies also poses a challenge for logistics companies. However, regulations and legal frameworks worldwide place significant pressure on logistics companies (Mohan & Amin, 20251-2).

While the storage is considered the most important element of the cold chain, the quality of warehouses and their design in accordance with technology have great importance. Measurement of temperature values, placement of products in the most ideal locations within the warehouse, management of power outages, determination of the optimal temperature to withstand temperature fluctuations, and separation of products into the correct groups within the warehouse, etc., are among the most important technical applications in the cold chain. Each of these applications enables the most efficient protection of temperature-sensitive products and components, while minimizing risks such as losses, increased production costs, and environmental damage (Pajić, Andrejić & Chatterjee, 2024).

From a logistics perspective, it is observed that companies across the sector are beginning to adopt a logistics approach centered on low-energy, environmentally friendly transportation, minimizing environmental impact and utilizing technological elements. Cold chain logistics vehicles, which feature cooling systems identical to those in warehouses, are being made more efficient and environmentally friendly by using electricity. The preference for digitally enhanced and environmentally friendly vehicles in land, sea, and air transportation ensures that the cold chain becomes sustainable and technologically advanced in a multifaceted way (Gao, 2019).

Sustainability and technological adaptation, which are of great importance in cold chain storage and cold chain logistics, are among the issues that logistics sector companies have attached great value to in recent years. Particularly in the food sector, the use of technology to minimize product waste involves improving the control of warehouses and logistics vehicles and increasing cooling capacities within the framework of energy efficiency. Issues such as temperature control, placement guidance, and temperature recommendations based on products make the sustainable use of technology in the cold chain possible (Gillespie et al., 2023).

Pharmaceutical storage and transportation, which can be considered another critical element of the cold chain, is an area where companies want to control temperature remotely using technological capabilities and digital elements. Accordingly, companies are seeking to use software and technical equipment to optimize cold storage systems, reduce medicine waste, and control the process even over long distances (Mendonça et al., 2021).

The concept of "green technology," which has come to the forefront in recent years, has reached a point of acceptance in terms of sustainable cold chain logistics. Green technology applications, which focus on performing all logistics activities with lower energy consumption, in a shorter time, and more efficiently with the support of technology, are now becoming established in cold chain logistics. Applications, programs, and technological tools in cold chain storage and cold chain logistics, which can be considered significant in terms of energy consumption, are seen as important for the future of the sector (Gibson, 2023).

Digitalized Sustainable Cold Chain Logistics: Profile of Lineage

About Lineage

Lineage, which entered the cold chain logistics sector in 2008 with a single cold storage facility, has strongly developed its sectoral identity over the years. By incorporating technological elements into the process, the company has enhanced the capacity of its commercial identity and become the world's largest temperature-controlled storage real estate investment trust. Recognizing that global warming, global food crises, and global pharmaceutical crises are the greatest threats to the world's future, the company develops its strategies by considering the issue from the perspectives of trade, sustainability, and digitalization (Lineage, 2026).

With annual revenues of \$5.3 billion based on 2025 data, the company is one of the largest in the sector with approximately 26,000 employees. Furthermore, these figures indicate that Lineage is the world's third-largest cold chain logistics company (Collins, 2025).

What makes Lineage significant in the industry is that its cold storage facilities are built with a great focus on energy efficiency. This makes the company a valued business partner, especially for food producers. Lineage, which also supports sustainable food projects, invests in sustainable technology elements to provide low-cost, high-quality storage services for both itself and its business partners. At the same time, Lineage, one of the largest cold chain storage and logistics companies in the US with the capacity to store a large number of food products, stands out as both a strong investment opportunity and a sustainable business partner (Stonepeak, 2026).

Currently, Lineage has transformed into a fully automated cold storage chain with its growth plans for 2025. The company plans to invest more than \$740 million in the development of its cold storage facilities and related technological infrastructure, constructing new warehouses with over 80 million cubic meters of space and a capacity of approximately 260,000 pallets. Currently, the company has one of the world's largest global temperature-controlled warehouses, with a network of more than 480 strategically located facilities across North America, Europe, and the Asia-Pacific region, totaling

84.1 million square meters and a capacity of 3.0 billion cubic meters. The company is focused on developing technologies that will minimize the supply chain (Business Wire, 2025).

Sustainability and Technology in Lineage

The software developed by Lineage and the company's sustainability activities demonstrate that this has become a corporate identity. Due to its industry-first practices and sustainability initiatives, Lineage has been named a CNBC Disruptor 50 Company for three consecutive years (2020, 2021, and 2022), twice named the Best Managed Company in the US, and ranked number 1 Data Science company in Fast Company's World's Most Innovative Companies list (ESG Today, 2023). Overall, Lineage has solidified its competitive edge by establishing itself as a leading software developer specializing in cold chain storage and logistics. The company's achievements, particularly its data-driven approach, are of significant importance.

Lineage's commitment to quality, efficient, and sustainable storage, which it considers critically important at the corporate level, is also applied to its clients for whom it provides consulting services in this area. The company, together with its data science team, analyzes the data of its business partners and customers using advanced modeling and then prepares a plan. This plan includes processes such as transportation and facility analysis, identifying suitable distribution centers and freight lines to create efficiency from production facilities to entry points and retail shelves. Lineage's data science team creates a plan by performing analyses based on information about its partners' and customers' historical shipment data, supplier and retailer locations, shipping costs, production locations, warehouse locations, and ports of entry or exit (Lineage, 2025a).

The company possesses the appropriate software, particularly in the areas of cold chain storage and cold chain transportation, to ensure that the process operates in a healthy, high-quality, and sustainable manner. "The application, called "Libra," is an algorithm designed to optimize the process of loading pallets of temperature-sensitive products into refrigerated trucks, ensuring they remain cold throughout their journey. Essentially, Libra collects pallet and vehicle information for outgoing shipments and then compares this information to specific requirements, including truck and vehicle dimensions and axle weight limits for those vehicles. This comparison determines the most suitable loading configuration based on the needs of the transported elements and the process. Libra calculates all possible scenarios for each transport element and process (Lineage, 2025b).

Lineage, as a cold chain storage company, possesses significant potential in this field, particularly in terms of software development, thanks to its unique operations and practices. At this point, the company's most trusted system is the "Sybil" software, which has adopted machine learning methods. The functions of Sybil that have a critical impact on cold chain storage systems can be listed as follows (Lineage, 2025c):

- Remembering the locations of pallets within the warehouse, providing placement information accordingly, and estimating suitable space for future pallet transfers.
- Adapting easily to changing storage conditions over time and managing change.

- Understanding and predicting seasonal changes in warehouses and protecting against seasonal risks with an appropriate storage layout.
- Guiding warehouse employees on layout, cost savings, planning, etc.
- Increasing the warehouse navigation skills of employees in terms of product picking and loading.

All of Sybil's capabilities, combined with Lineage's cold storage facilities, enable Lineage's supply chain partners and stakeholders to achieve significant savings in time, space, and materials, as well as more efficient use of energy and materials in the warehouses. Furthermore, Sybil prevents employees from wasting time by creating extra seating plans and choosing unnecessary transportation options.

At Lineage, the scanning and sorting of incoming products and other items at the warehouse is a critical aspect of the warehousing process for the later stages of logistics. "Lineage Eye," developed for this application, is a critical guiding mechanism for cold chain storage and logistics. Lineage Eye, by quickly capturing the exterior and barcode numbers of incoming products and other items from different angles, determines the location of products and other items, identifies customers, reveals transportation details, and quickly detects any errors or omissions, alerting authorities accordingly. This process, which takes place in seconds, facilitates the work of Lineage officials and business partners in an artificially enhanced manner (Lineage, 2025d).

Lineage, which has the ability to create solutions not only for its own operations but also for the companies it works with, can identify the nearest and most cost-effective warehouses for sustainable logistics activities using various data analysis methods. The company evaluates historical shipment data, supplier and retailer locations, transportation costs, production sites, warehouse locations, and entry or exit ports with the most detailed data, in line with its customers' needs. Thanks to this, the company's data system can rank warehouses and logistics partners offering the most suitable, high-quality, and easiest access networks to shipping points for a customer, from the most useful to the least useful. This results in significant time and cost savings for a company (Lineage, 2025e).

The company has adopted the principles of more space, less energy, and more technology assistance in constructing its warehouses for both storage and logistics purposes based on sustainable technology. Lineage warehouses, constructed with high ceilings and high racking, maintain the existing cold air for extended periods thanks to the high ceilings, which also offers the opportunity for lower energy consumption. At the same time, the company's digital applications and automation system are being adapted to the multi-bay and crowded warehouse. Studies show that warehouses operating in this way will experience approximately a 20% reduction in kWh usage per pallet in 2024 compared to traditional warehouses. Faster loading and unloading operations through automation also make the company's employees' jobs easier in terms of reduced energy costs (Lineage, 2025f).

On the other hand, Lineage implements its carbon emission strategy for each of its operations according to its own rules. The company, which does not require any commitment in this regard, strives to manage its carbon emission process in a healthy manner based on the energy consumption

of its extremely large-capacity storage facilities. Accordingly, the company uses solar panels in its cold storage facilities across the US and in various locations around the world. The company, which powers its warehouses with solar energy, is making significant investments in this area, and through compatible software developed by the company, solar energy is consumed in a controlled manner. At the same time, energy obtained from solar panels enables the company's storage, loading and transportation activities to be carried out in a coordinated and low-carbon manner (Lineage, 2025f).

It can be said that Lineage's technological advancements, particularly those aimed at improving the quality of its warehouses and transport vehicles, have made a significant difference in the industry. Among these, variable-speed compressors stand out with their unique feature are differ from the on/off mode system of traditional compressors, which leads to inefficiency. Variable speed technology is based on the principle of increasing or decreasing the speed of cooling systems depending on thermal demand. This variation minimizes energy fluctuations, equipment wear, and overall power consumption. This system, which provides an average annual energy saving of 34%, enables products from the pharmaceutical, food, and retail sectors to be stored efficiently in warehouses simultaneously and transferred when the time comes (The Logistics Navigators, 2025).

Conclusion

While the logistics sector is crucial for the development of all industries and the sustainability of trade worldwide, the cold chain occupies a critical position within logistics. Cold chain logistics plays a vital role in ensuring the lossless or minimally lost transportation of products from various sectors, including food and pharmaceuticals. The starting point of the process is cold chain storage practices. The quality of storage conditions determines the quality of other stages of trade, and at this point, it is critically important to prefer and implement technologically compatible and sustainable policies in the process that begins with storage, continues with logistics, and ends with delivery to the end user.

The logistics sector, which is generous in its consumption of many different elements, especially energy, needs to be more compatible with the environment and social interests. Sustainability, a topic of importance not only for governments but for all companies, is a particularly prominent issue in logistics, especially in warehousing and transportation activities. As a result of both environmental awareness and the effective role of technology within the system, the logistics sector is striving to use sustainability and technology effectively and simultaneously through the cold chain.

Lineage, selected as a model company in the research, is one of the examples that successfully blends technology and sustainability within the logistics sector. Not only is Lineage a leading example in its own cold chain warehousing and logistics operations, but it also serves as a model for its business partners, adopting a collective approach to sustainable logistics. The company's high-quality software, along with its comprehensive cost-saving, efficiency, and sustainability capabilities, positions it as a leader in its field.

Viewed from another perspective, Lineage actually represents the direction and future of perceptions within the industry regarding cold chain storage and logistics. Lineage, being a pioneer in the digitalization process in its field, both for itself and for companies like it, thus also holds the position of a sectoral future planner in terms of cold chain storage and logistics. The company identifies

shortcomings in its sector in terms of sustainability and efficiency and strives to develop unique solutions tailored to these needs.

Libra, Sybil, and Lineage Eye software are three key technological assets of the company, demonstrating its high level of sustainability awareness in terms of energy, time, and material savings. More importantly, the fact that these three software programs were developed by Lineage elevates the company beyond being a traditional logistics company. Lineage, in this respect, considers the sustainable identity of the technologies it develops while planning, designing, managing, and directing every stage of cold chain logistics. The company's sustainability and technology-focused activities aimed at saving space, time, materials, and energy appear to be among the leading practices in the sector.

References

Azira, B., Norhayati, M. N. & Norwati, D. (2013). Knowledge, Attitude and Adherence to Cold Chain among General Practitioners in Kelantan, Malaysia. *International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health*, 5(3), 157-167.

Beldar, S. S. (2025). AI and robotics in cold chain logistics: Overcoming the barriers to full automation. *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*, 15(03), 812-819.

Bogataj, M., Bogataj, L. & Vodopivec, R. (2005). Stability of perishable goods in cold logistic chains. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 93–94, 345-56.

Business Wire (2025). Lineage, Inc. Announces Plans to Expand Its U.S. Cold-Storage Network With Long-Time Customer. <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20250430683093/en/Lineage-Inc.-Announces-Plans-to-Expand-Its-U.S.-Cold-Storage-Network-With-Long-Time-Customer>

Collins, L. (2025). Top 10: Cold Chain Logistics Companies. Supply Chain Digital. <https://supplychaindigital.com/top10/top-10-cold-chain-logistics-companies>

ESG Today (2023). Lineage Showcases Commitment to Environmental Stewardship and Corporate Citizenship in Inaugural Sustainability Report. <https://www.esgtoday.com/lineage-showcases-commitment-to-environmental-stewardship-and-corporate-citizenship-in-inaugural-sustainability-report/>

Fuente, M. V. & Ros, L. (2010). *Cold Supply Chain Processes in a Fruit-and-Vegetable Collaborative Network*, “Balanced Automation Systems for Future Manufacturing Networks: 9th IFIP WG 5.5 International Conference, BASYS 2010, Valencia, Spain, July 21-23, 2010, 3-10.

Gao, H. (2019). Analysis of New Energy-saving Technology for Cold Chain Logistics. *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 252, 1-5.

Gibson, P. A. (2023). Shortening the Supply Chain through Smart Manufacturing and Green Technology. *Sustainability*, 15, 1-11.

Gillespie, J. et. al (2023). Real-time anomaly detection in cold chain transportation using IoT technology. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 1-24.

Lineage (2025a). How Data Science Builds Smarter Supply Chains. https://www.onelineage.com/sites/default/files/2025-10/0063-11_LL_CstmrCsStdy_NetworkAnalysis_1920x6600_LR.pdf

Lineage (2025b). Introducing Libra: The Lineage Algorithm Optimizing How We Load Trucks. <https://www.onelineage.com/news-stories/libra-algorithm-optimize-truck-loading>

Lineage (2025c). The Self-Awarehouse: Unleashing Lineage's Algorithms in Warehouse Operations. <https://www.onelineage.com/news-stories/self-awarehouse-unleashing-lineages-algorithms-warehouse-operations>

Lineage (2025d). Data Reliability: How Lineage Technology is Reducing Errors and Improving Inventory Accuracy. <https://www.onelineage.com/news-stories/technology-improving-inventory-accuracy>

Lineage (2025e). The science behind smarter supply chains: How one Lineage analysis found \$2 million in annual savings. <https://www.onelineage.com/news-stories/science-behind-smarter-supply-chains>

Lineage (2025f). Sustainability Report. https://www.onelineage.com/sites/default/files/2025-06/Lineage-2024-Sustainability-Report_6_25_25.pdf

Lineage (2026). A story of growth and success. <https://www.onelineage.com/about-us/heritage>

Mendonça, R. D. et al. (2021). BlockColdChain: Vaccine Cold Chain Blockchain. *Authorea*, (March, 2021), 1-13.

Mohan, M. & Amin, S. (2025). Green Cold Chain Logistics: Minimising Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Fresh Food Products in Transport Refrigeration Units. *Green Cold Chain Logistics: Minimising Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Fresh Food Products in Transport Refrigeration Units. Logistics*, 9(112), 1-17.

Pajić, V., Andrejić, A. & Chatterjee, P. (2024). Enhancing Cold Chain Logistics: A Framework for Advanced Temperature Monitoring in Transportation and Storage. *Mechatronics and Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 3(1), 16-30.

Pindi, M. (2025). Revolutionizing cold chain logistics: Leveraging IoT and AI for enhanced food safety and waste reduction. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 26(02), 1412-1424.

Saravanan, S. & Anubama, B. (2017). Selection of Cold Chain Logistics Service Providers in Pharmaceutical Industry with Reference to India. *International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains*, 8(2), 1-12.

Stonepeak (2026). Reimagining the world's food supply chain. <https://stonepeak.com/portfolio-highlights/lineage-logistics>

The Logistics Navigators (2025). Lineage Logistics: How a Quiet Roll-Up Became the Cold Chain King. <https://www.logisticsnavigators.com/businessbreakdowns/lineage-logistics-how-a-quiet-roll-up-became-the-cold-chain-king>

Thompson, C. L. (2016). Cold Chain Transportation for Medical Operations due to the Heat Conditions. *Developed Pharmacy*, (17), 19-34.

Wang, W. (2016). Cold Chain Logistics Development and Analysis of Necessity. *Journal of Service Science and Management*, (9), 238-242.

Yuen, S. S. M. (2017). Temperature Controlled Warehouse and Cold Chain Business In Hong Kong: A Literature Review. *Asia Pacific Institute of Advanced Research*, 3(1), 8-18.